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Short Communication

Are We Doing Enough to Stop Bullying of Muslim Students in Public Schools?

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Abstract

Promoting diversity and employing programs that advocate tolerance and plurality must be equally important to educators and policy makers. Unfortunately, Muslim students nowadays are faced with bigotry and bullying at an alarming level. These students are in desperate need for help to fight against racial discrimination and bullying at their schools. The author of this study investigated the volume of empirical research in education literature that addressed bullying against Muslim students in U.S. public schools using GALILEO, an online library search system, and Google Scholar search engine. Results showed that less than 0.1% of the searched literature on bullying addressed Muslim students. This study also investigated educational policies and strategies to combat bullying against Muslim students as well as the commitment of educators and policy makers to eradicate such phenomenon.

Keywords: Muslim students, bullying, Public Schools, Diversity, Plurality, Tolerance

1 Introduction

Incidents of bullying against Muslim students in U.S. public schools are rarely investigated by researchers; hence risking understanding the psychological impact on the well-being of the bullied students. In addition to negative images and covert discrimination against Islam in certain media outlets, Muslim students are enduring bullying at their schools on a consistent basis. According to a 2016 report on Islamophobia by UC Berkeley Center for Race and Gender (CRG) and the Council on American-Islamic Relations (CAIR), more than 55% of Muslim students in California have been victims of Islamophobic bullying at schools (CAIR, 2016). A study conducted by Baadarani (2016) showed that Muslim students in high schools experience bullying at a rate of 53% compared to a national rate of 20%. The study also revealed that religion is a predictor variable that hinders the development of cultural identity of Muslim students due to bullying and harassment. Sirin and Fine (2007) reported 85% of Muslim students experienced discrimination because of their religion and ethnical background. Most of these students did not report these incidents and chose to deal with bullying on their own. The result was a prominent increase in anxiety and degradation in their social and behavioral development.

The purpose of this study is to assess the current state of research in relation to bullying against Muslim students and the counter measures, if any, that are deployed by policy makers and educators to confront such bigotry and injustice. It also proposes a framework of guidelines and strategies by which all stakeholders can benefit from when dealing with Muslim students who are at risk of being bullied.

2 Theoretical Framework

Establishing a robust program that teaches pre-service teachers anti-bullying strategies has been a challenge to teacher preparation programs

within the general education setting due to curriculum requirements and resistance to buy-in of such programs by various stakeholders (Gorsek & Cunningham, 2014). Furthermore, bullying has not been found to be connected to one specific cause (Swearer-Napolitano, 2011). However, researchers identified a list of factors that can be attributed to the abnormal behaviors of bullying, such as poor social skills, aggression and violence towards themselves and others, hyperactivity, and difficulty with academics. Bullies may also show greater hostility, physical tantrums, or even disengagement from reality (Coolidge, DenBoer, & Segal, 2004).

Rock, Hammond, and Rasmussen (2002) advocated the use of empathy to reduce all types of bullying behaviors, while Maarouf and Jones (2016) proposed empathy as an intervention method to combat bullying of Muslim students. Ramarajan and Runell (2007) proposed the use of cooperative learning model to reduce prejudice in students and to address developmental appropriateness and multiculturalism in classrooms.

The author of this study posit that empathy, relational pedagogy, and cooperative learning models that were proposed in prior research can be coalesced by implementing motivation strategies that engage students and ensure successful outcomes. Motivation is a broad subject that is covered by many theories and can be looked at from five viewpoints – behavioral, humanistic, cognitive, social-cognitive, and socio-cultural (Woolfolk, 2011). The benefits of implementing motivation techniques in any classroom setting are well documented in the literature (Urduan & Maehr, 2009; Meece, Anderman, & Anderman, 2006; Nichols & Utesch, 1998).

3 Methods and data Sources

The author used GeorgiA Library Learning Online (GALILEO) to search for peer-reviewed publications and Google Scholar search engine to find relevant work addressing bullying against Muslim students. GALILEO is Georgia's online virtual library system established in 1995 by the Board

of Regents of the University System of Georgia. It is used by more than 2000 institutions and accesses over 100 databases indexing thousands of journals, magazines, ebooks, government publications, etc. (GALILEO, n.d.). Google Scholar is a free search engine that provides a simple way to search for abstracts, articles, books, and other scholarly research (Google Scholar, n.d.). Although its search options are limited, Google Scholar can perform deep web search accessing scholarly research across the world.

For the GALILEO search, the author limited the results to only peer-reviewed articles. The search started with using the word “bullying” and then an “AND” Boolean operator was used to add the following words in the following order: “public schools”, “United States”, and “Muslim students”. For Google Scholar search, the author used Google Scholar search box with the same order of adding words as was done with GALILEO search. Google Scholar is not as robust as GALILEO when it comes to search options and the use of Boolean operators. Results from both search methods were constrained to articles that were published post 9/11 attacks (2001 to 2017). The author finally screened the titles and abstracts of the last GALILEO and Google Scholar searches and obliterated the articles that were deemed not relevant to the topic of this study.

4 Results

Sadly, we do not know much about the role of race or religion in bullying since there has not been adequate academic research in this space (Swearer-Napolitano, 2011; Abada, Hou, & Ram, 2008). Nevertheless, it is well documented in the literature that Muslim and Jewish students are subjected to more bullying than other religions and students of color are bullied more than White students (Schools' Toolkit, n.d.). Abo-Zena et al. (2009) stated that “Hostile behavior and bullying in school settings is a common reality for Muslim students, evidenced by incidents of discrimination that have occurred nationwide in the classroom, in the cafeteria, during extra-curricular activities, and on the school bus...” (Abo-Zena, Sahli, & Tobias-Nahi, 2009, p.5).

Table 1. Number of Articles Using GALILEO and Google Scholar Search Engines

Search Word/s	GALILEO	Google Scholar
bullying	120,604	269,000
+ public schools	62,992	70,300
+ Unites States	42,436	40,500
+ Muslim students	96	1,250
relevancy to topic	24	182
% of articles discussing bullying Muslim students	0.057%	0.449%

Number of articles related to bullying

Table 1 shows that GALILEO search yielded 120,604 articles related to “bullying”, 62,992 articles related to “bullying in public schools”, 42,436 articles related to “bullying in the United States public schools”, and only 96 articles related to “bullying in the United States public schools against Muslim students”. Images 1 to 4 show screenshots of the results for each of the searches. After further review of the 96 articles, the author determined that there were only 24 articles relevant to the topic of this study. This number constitutes only 0.057% of the total peer-reviewed articles that discussed bullying in U.S. public schools system (24 out of 42,436).

Image 1. GALILEO search “bullying”

Image 2. GALILEO search “bullying AND public schools”

Image 3. GALILEO search “bullying AND public schools AND United States”

Image 4. GALILEO search “bullying AND public schools AND United States AND Muslim students”

The Google Scholar search yielded 269,000 articles related to “bullying”, 70,300 articles related to “bullying in public schools”, 40,500 articles related to “bullying in the United States public schools”, and 1,250 articles related to “bullying in the United States public schools against Muslim students”. Images 5 to 8 show screenshots of the results for each of the searches. After further review of the 1,250 articles, the author determined that there were only 182 articles relevant to the topic of this study. This

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number constitutes only 0.449% of the total articles that discussed bullying in the U.S. public schools system (182 out of 40,500). Most of the Google Scholar results related to bullying of Muslim students were web pages that were deemed by Google algorithm that they are “scholarly”. It is noteworthy here that the accuracy of the free service of Google Scholar search engine has been questioned by some researchers in regards to its lack of screen for quality and vulnerability to spam (Beel & Gipp, 2010; Oliver, 2010; Kulkarni et al., 2009).

Image 5. Google Scholar search “bullying”

Image 6. Google Scholar search “bullying public schools”

Image 7. Google Scholar search “bullying public schools U.S.”

Image 8. Google Scholar search “bullying public schools U.S. Muslim students”

5 Discussion and Recommendation

To address the negative outcomes of bullying against Muslim students, a developmental framework consisting of new legislation and classroom strategies should be implemented by policy makers and educators in order to identify particular periods and modes for intervention. A holistic approach that integrates legislation and teaching strategies would be ideal to avoid any public backlash due to addressing religion in educational settings.

5.1 What Education Policy Makers can do?

Education policy makers must realize the danger of Islamophobic bullying that is taking place in public schools. This growing intolerance against Muslim students must be met with a swift action by legislators to pass tougher laws that respect diversity and teach civil responsibilities. A report by CAIR (2014) demonstrated that Muslim students experience bullying two times the rate of other students and these offenses, regrettably, were committed by their peers as well as teachers. Conceivably, one of the greatest impediments to promote educational policies that confront Islamophobic bullying is the fear of addressing religion at schools. Although teaching religion at schools has been a highly debated topic in our society and in the U.S. courts system, teaching religious diversity has been embraced by the courts and is protected by the First Amendment of the U.S. constitution (Ramarajan & Runell, 2007). Hence, education policy makers need to construct a plan that ends offensive behavior towards Muslim students and address inadequacy in protecting these students without being afraid of anti-Islamic sentiment in the public arena.

Unfortunately, the author of this study did not find any empirical research in this space. A government sponsored programs that support and finance sustainable research that aim to derive educational policies based on empirical evidence will go a long way in promoting tolerance and respect for diversity. Furthermore, education policy makers can work with school leaders to implement the following policies:

- Advocate for more culturally effective pedagogies.
- Ensure personal commitment of school leaders and other school management team members and hold them accountable in driving concrete measures that combat Islamophobic bullying.
- Provide incentives to school leaders and teachers who value inclusive school culture and combat exclusion and intolerance.
- Build bridges that connect schools with their communities.

5.2 What Educators can do?

Teachers can apply simple strategies that can make a substantial difference in the life of a bullied Muslim child. Some of these strategies could include giving bullied children a lead job in the classroom, commenting on their religious identity, posting work related to their cultural background, reading books in the classroom about prominent U.S. Muslim individuals who greatly contributed to our country, offering structured exercises that help them to interact with their peers, and keeping a close eye on them so that they do not become victims of frequent bullying.

Unfortunately, first year teachers start their career lacking the proper professional development knowledge to effectively deal with bullying (Craig, Bell, & Leschied, 2011; Bauman & Rio, 2006). During college years, these teachers would benefit from additional training related to anti-bullying strategies, understanding students who are victims of bullying, understanding students with emotional and/or behavioral disorders, and applying strategies to boost positive behaviors and discourage negative ones. Furthermore, teachers should understand the difficulties that bullied students experience in several areas of their academic and social lives such as learning, relationships with their peers, and self-esteem.

6 Conclusion

Educators have a fundamental role in teaching acceptance of each other and in combating intolerance and racial discrimination. Policy makers provide educators the legal means in the field of education to fight against inequality and hostilities against minority groups. If defeating bullying against Muslim students is our goal, then it is our ethical responsibility as educators and policy makers to search and provide the support each child actually needs. The findings from this study indicated that bullying against Muslim students in the U.S. is not well-represented in the literature. The inadequacy of such research will have grievous consequences on the lives of the bullied students. More systemic data collection and research is needed to show what works in combating discrimination against Muslim students and in promoting cultural diversity.

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Writing Success and Self Efficacy: The Student Perspective

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Abstract

Studies show that student revisions culminate in more expansive, finely researched, and effectively composed essays (Kolb, 1982, Bruner, 1970). While there has been much focus on how the amount and variety of teacher and peer feedback impacts student revisions, there has been little research focusing specifically on developmental composition students and the ways in which they process and utilize feedback and, consequently, the impact of feedback on both student essays and self-efficacy. This study, therefore, addressed these issues through the lens of the student perspective. Employing semi-structured interviews and observation, two developmental composition students and their instructor from a small, private university in Western New York participated in this qualitative study. Research sought to understand how teacher practices impacted developmental writing students' ability to interpret and respond to peer and teacher feedback, their use of secondary support systems, such as the writing center, how these things impacted the revision process, and how their learning experience influenced both student writing and self-efficacy. The results suggested that without foundational knowledge and modeling, feedback was cursory and unproductive, leaving students unable to make meaningful revisions to essays. This, to some extent, led to low self-efficacy and fear of writing.

Keywords: Developmental writers, feedback, modelling, revision process, college-level composition, teacher practices.

Introduction

Millions of teenagers begin college each year, and the vast majority of those freshmen are required to take a composition class. Here, students are taught the finer points of persuasion, how to compose thought-provoking, compelling essays. They learn about scholarly research and the ethical use of information. These students also gain insights about clear, logical organization and audience impact. Perhaps most foundational, these students are taught the writing process, a process which entails non-linear steps such as pre-writing, drafting, revising, and proofreading. Revising is, potentially, one of the most important aspects of the writing process. William Zinsser (2006), author of 18 books, including *On Writing Well*, believes, "Rewriting is the essence of writing well—where the game is won or lost". For the average student, while perhaps less than riveting, the class serves its purpose. Undergraduates master the skills necessary for success in composition class, and perhaps more important, they now have the tools for success throughout college. College enrollment, however, is not exclusively limited to average and above-average students.

As of 2011, only 26 percent of college undergraduates fit the profile of "traditional" students, while the remainder and overwhelming majority, 74 percent, might be labeled non-traditional (Garcia Mathewson, 2015). These students may postpone entrance or attend on a part-time basis, or they might be considered financially independent and may have dependents of their own. A number of these non-traditional students have even foregone earning a high school diploma, opting for either a GED or other certificate of completion (Bruch et al., 2004, p.12). These characteristics, however, are not what educational institutions are concerned about. Instead, it is the level of preparedness these students, both traditional and non-traditional, arrive with. According to Mario Fusaro (2009), only 32 percent are ready to handle the academic challenges they will face (p.1). Without the necessary support, few of these students will successfully complete a degree. Some assistance comes in the form of developmental classes, most often Reading, Writing, and Math. In 2011, over 33 percent of incoming freshmen required some form of remediation, and the numbers are even higher at community colleges (U.S. DOE, 2017). According to Remedial Education in Higher Education Institutions (1998), 41 percent of incoming freshmen are likely to enroll in remedial courses (p.3). Many of these students will be

placed in developmental composition classes where they must acquire skills for academic success; effective composing processes and critical thinking. Without these skills, students are unable to participate fully in the feedback process, and without benefit of rich, meaningful feedback and reflection, substantive revision does not occur. This gap in learning not only hinders writing, it can leave students feeling frustrated and incapable. Believing themselves incapable, they might well attempt to circumvent future writing tasks and avoidance can signal academic disaster. This concern acted as the impetus for research. Because developmental learners too often arrive at college having experienced little success in writing, it is of paramount importance that teachers identify and utilize theory and methods that serve to strengthen student skills, and in doing so, we may find their self-efficacy rise proportionately. This study, then, sought to better understand the needs of developmental writing students and how those needs, met or unmet, impact student writing and self-efficacy.

Research Questions

Research questions that guided this study include:

1. How does task understanding and strategy acquisition impact student drafting and feedback?
2. How do students perceive the quality and usefulness of teacher and peer feedback?
3. How productive was the revision process, both real and perceived?
4. How confident are students about future writing projects?

Theoretical Framework

Although little research focuses on developmental composition specifically, there is an abundance of theory surrounding and supporting current pedagogy in writing classes. Because my primary interest was in how student learning impacts feedback, and how that feedback impacts writing, and consequently self-efficacy, I referred to Vygotsky's social development theory which espouses social learning, along with incremental assistance by both instructors and peers. In concert, these methods, theory says, allow for knowledge acquisition and self-sufficiency. Bruner's scaffolding theory builds on Vygotsky's theory, addressing the merits of student feedback specifically. The writing process plays a pivotal role, helping students to identify and meet goals while immersed in thought and composition, while Dewey's inquiry-based learning theory addresses the need to connect writing to the lived worlds of students. Bandura's social cognitive theory and Zimmerman and Bonner's Social Cognitive Model of Sequential Skill Acquisition point to the importance of modeling for writing success and self-efficacy.

Vygotsky's Social Development Theory

Vygotsky's (1978) Social Development Theory maintains that learning occurs socially. Community plays a decisive role in the process of "meaning making" for a child. Learning is constructed socially, and points away from the traditional instructionist model of education; where teachers transmit information, and students act as receptacles. In opposition, Vygotsky's theory

maintains the need for active learning, creating a classroom environment in which teacher and student act as collaborators, facilitating meaning construction for the student and yielding reciprocal learning for both parties. While the teacher's task is altered, the part they play in the learning process is of paramount importance. In a writing class, this translates into a community of trust and respect, essential elements for productive draft critiquing.

Vygotsky (1978) also believed that "more knowledgeable others" (MKOs), including teachers and "more competent peers", can aid in student development (p.86). This belief underlies Vygotsky's principle of the ZPD, the zone of proximal development. "What a child can do with assistance today she will be able to do by herself tomorrow" (p.87). This is an important concept in regards to writing ability, even at the college level. Bearing in mind the number of freshmen who lack the skill and training necessary for utilizing and composing scholarly research that informs, encouragement and guidance from more skilled partners has the potential to assist in cognitive transformation and knowledge expansion. A quintessential example of how MKOs aid in student learning is through the use of scaffolding.

Bruner's Scaffolding Theory

Vygotsky never actually used the term "scaffolding". Instead, it was Jerome Bruner, a follower of Vygotsky, who coined it. (Clay & Cazden, 1990). According to Harris and Hodges in their *The Literacy Dictionary* (1996), scaffolding is:

In learning, the gradual withdrawal of adult (eg teacher) support, as through instruction, modeling, questioning, feedback etc., for a child's performance across successive engagements, thus transferring more autonomy to the child.

The feedback from both teachers and peers, referred to by Clay & Cazden (1990), might include elucidating activities such as posing pertinent questions, offering insights and suggestions, and, as students actively participate, both offering and receiving thoughtful, thought-provoking responses, bridges between reading, writing, and thinking are built. Students gain academic independence as their level of knowledge, confidence and self-efficacy increases.

The concept of scaffolding is quintessential to the writing process, but neither scaffolding nor the writing process was practiced until the 1970's. Before that, following rhetorical traditions dating back to the nineteenth century, students would be assigned essays in the forms of description, narration, exposition, or argument. Teachers would school students on the ideal written product, their focus on words, sentences, and paragraphs as component parts, with the emphasis on style and usage. These essays, these finished products, were graded on the merit of compliance to form and conventions (Hodges, 1991). Thankfully, process theory of composition marked the beginning of a major pedagogical paradigm shift in writing education and this sort of antithetical approach to writing was soon abandoned.

Writing Process Theory

Composition scholars such as Janet Emig, Peter Elbow, and Donald Murray envisioned writing as a process, a process that focused on student interest, voice, and personal technique (Murray, 2011). Murray (2011) contended, "Instead of teaching finished writing, we should teach unfinished writing, and glory in its unfinishedness" (p.4). Contrary to traditionalists, Murray's process theory emphasized, "...the process of discovery through language" (p.5), and while Janet Emig (1971) broke the writing process down to distinct parts, it was Murray who simplified it, creating a three-step process: Prewriting, writing, and rewriting (also called "revision"). Participation and experimentation during the process allows composition students to find their voices, hone persuasive skills and exercise meaningful reflection.

Dewey's Inquiry-Based Learning Theory

Confucius (450 BC) is credited with the proverb, "Tell me, and I will forget. Show me, and I may remember. Involve me, and I will understand". This seems to mirror Dewey's rationale for inquiry-based learning which focuses on learning-by-doing rather than rote memorization and instruction. Predating Vygotsky by some thirty years, Dewey (1902) envisioned the classroom as neither entirely child-based nor entirely curriculum-centered. Instead, he maintained, "The child and the curriculum are simply two limits which define a single process. Just as two points define a straight line, so the present standpoint of the child and the facts and truths of studies define instruction" (Dewey, 1902, p. 16). It was this line of reasoning that propelled Dewey to become one of the most famous and vocal proponents of hands-on learning (Dewey, 1902, p. 13-14). Though written more than a century ago, Dewey (1897) seems to respond to the topic of teacher feedback, encouraging instructors to act as facilitators: "The teacher is not in the school to impose certain ideas or to form certain habits in the child, but is there as a member of the community to select the influences which shall affect the child and to assist him in properly responding to these influences" (p. 9). Perhaps then, we, as teachers, should be focused less on what our students believe and more focused on helping them identify why they believe what they do, and how to most effectively persuade readers of the validity of those beliefs. This can only be accomplished with well researched, effectively composed essays, the kind that feedback and revisions yield.

Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory

At its core, social cognitive theory maintains that people learn from observing others (Bandura, 1988). Originally concerned with modeling as it relates to aggressive behavior, social cognitive theory also pertains to the process of knowledge acquisition from the observation of models. Effective modeling teaches general rules and strategies, including those used in composition. In education, it is the teacher who acts as the model. This precipitates learning acquisition and also aids in building students' self-efficacy through acknowledgement and praise for incremental improvement.

Zimmerman and Bonner's Social Cognitive Model of Sequential Skill Acquisition

This model posits that students learn through a developmental progression which begins socially, through modeling, and culminates in self-regulation, a student's ability to employ and utilize knowledge (Zimmerman, 2000). In order to acquire necessary skills, first teachers must model, in this case writing, then imitation; student exploration. These activities, according to the model, cause skills to become internalized, represented as self-control. Eventually, self-regulation allows students to act independent of socially-driven motivators. This translates well in writing class where after modeling, students become immersed in self-envisioned, self-created works of writing.

4 Literature Review

Teacher Feedback

Teacher feedback is of paramount importance for both student writing and student revisions (Peterson & Kennedy, 2004; Sommers, 2006; Stagg, Peterson & Kennedy, 2006; Stern & Solomon, 2006). Do students care about receiving feedback on their writing? Research answers with a resounding "Yes!" In a longitudinal study, Nancy Sommers (1982) followed 400 Harvard undergraduates through their college careers to understand the role that writing plays in undergraduate education. While considered by many to be a seminal study, she revisited the subject some 25 years later in a continuing attempt to ascertain ways to improve composition instruction. Referring to her 1982 study, she reflects:

What emerged in every conversation we had with students about their college writing is the power of feedback, its absence or presence, to shape their writing experiences. As one student told me, "Without a reader, the whole process is diminished". That students care deeply about the comments they receive was revealed in our survey of 400 students, who were asked as juniors to offer one piece of advice to improve writing instruction at Harvard. Overwhelmingly-almost 90 percent-they responded: urge faculty to give more specific comments (p.251).

While research on feedback during the composition process is sparse, there is overwhelming evidence that students are looking for feedback, whether during or upon completion of projects and many students believe feedback they receive to be inadequate. Literature emphasizes students' frustration with feedback lacking details and suggestions for improvement (Higgins et al., 2001), as well as feedback that's difficult to interpret (Chanock, 2000). Studies out of the UK reflect the same level of student dissatisfaction. Scott's 2006 study focused on students across 14 Australian universities. 90 percent of those polled believe instructor feedback needs improvement. Some of the problems cited include the quality and quantity received, as well as inconsistencies. The report also suggested that quality control was especially in need of attention within higher education. Conversely, instructors are frustrated by how little revision reflects feedback offered by these faculty members. Research by Mutch (2003), Lea and Street (1998) and Ivanic et al. (2000) maintains that, contrary to popular belief, minimal adherence to revision suggestions is not due to

slovenly work ethics but lack of understanding. Instructor feedback, "...is codified in the 'expert' language of academic disciplines" (Orrell, 2006, p.441). Not only does Orrell (2006) find much of the feedback blurred by the language, but that which is understood focuses on errors rather than potential strengths. This has a detrimental effect on student egos (p.441).

Peer Feedback

Peer assessment is defined as "...an arrangement in which individuals consider the amount, level, value, worth, quality, or success of the products or outcomes of learning of peers of similar status" (Topping, 1998, p. 250). That is what teachers hope students will consider in responding to peers but how equipped for the task are they? While research on the benefits of peer feedback is abundant, there is an equivalent dearth of research on the subject of student preparation for the task of responding to peer essays. Flower et al. (1986) identify four functions of peer feedback: analysis, evaluation, explanation, and revision. In order to critique an essay adequately, one need analyze it and provide ample explanations. The receiver needs concrete, understandable arguments, from which revision will be executed. In a rare study conducted by Van den Berg et al. (2006), seven designs of peer assessment were tested for effectiveness among 168 students and nine teachers at Utrecht University, one of the oldest in the Netherlands. Ultimately, their research pointed to an optimal model which incorporates six important design features:

1. Product: the size of the writing is five to eight pages. The reason is that students will not be willing to invest enough time in assessing larger products.
2. Relation to staff assessment: there must be sufficient time between the peer assessment and teacher assessment, so that students can first revise their papers on the basis of peer feedback, and then hand it in to the teacher.
3. Directionality: two-way feedback is easier to organize for teacher and students, as it is clear that the assessor will in turn be the assessee, which makes it easier to exchange products. Oral feedback during class will not take much time, because the feedback groups can discuss simultaneously.
4. Contact: verbal explanation, analysis and suggestions for revision are necessary elements of the feedback process; these require face-to-face contact.
5. Constellation assessors/assesseees: the size of feedback groups has to be three or four. In that situation, students have an opportunity to compare their fellow students' remarks, and to determine their relevance. A group of two students is too small, because of the risk that the partner might not perform properly.
6. Place: oral feedback must be organised during contact hours, because it is difficult to ascertain if students will organise this themselves when out of class. ICT -tools can be used to enable students to read the peer feedback before discussing it. (p.34-35)

Note the extensive considerations given to how maximized feedback might be cultivated. Conversely, consider too how little

might be gained if similar consideration is not given. All feedback is not created equally. Research conducted by Yang's 2006 study determined that, in consideration of performance, while students believed they benefitted from peer feedback, participants benefitted more from teacher feedback in the areas of both impact and improvement. Before feedback, however, sound pedagogical practices lay the foundation for successful writing. Without adequate instruction and modeling, especially in developmental composition classes, students may be ill-equipped to craft first drafts or offer feedback that yields substantial revision. Success or failure during the writing process has profound implications for students' sense of self efficacy.

The Impact of Feedback on Self Efficacy

Although not the only determiner, feedback that teachers offer can either positively or negatively impact student motivation and engagement in learning (Alderman 2004; Brophy 1981; Dolezal et al. 2003; Mastropieri and Scruggs 2004; Pintrich and Schunk 2002; Stipek 2001). Schunk et. al's 1993 study investigated how progress feedback, along with goal setting, affected both self-efficacy and writing achievement. Research concluded that feedback, especially in concert with progress goal setting, strongly impacted self-efficacy. This study is pertinent because it considered the complex relationship between strategy acquisition, feedback, self-efficacy and writing performance. Drawing on Bandura's social cognitive theory, Schunk found that as students meet goals, self-efficacy increases. This increased sense of agency acts as a motivator in future endeavors, hence impacting the quality of writing. Self-efficacy was, in turn, highly predictive of writing skill and strategy use. While Cynthia Ozick is credited with saying writing is an act of courage, teachers need to be cognizant of the fear many students harbor, especially in relation to their writing abilities. As May and Rizzardi (2002) stated, "Half the battle in teaching is just getting children to take a chance with their self-esteem and try new tasks. If students feel they cannot be successful, the result will typically be what is termed 'work avoidance'" (p. 331). Lack of self-efficacy not only signals failure for that student, it also impacts their willingness and confidence to offer feedback to classmates, feedback that stimulates cognitive development and strengthens critical analysis abilities for both reader and writer. Research by Smith et al. (2005) shows peer review aids students in improving not just their critical thinking and evaluative skills, but also the precision with which they express their thoughts and ideas. As students' master language and subject knowledge, self-esteem and self-confidence increases. As cognitive development is enhanced, both attitude towards the course and their satisfaction is increased (Goldschmid and Goldschmid, 1976; Topping, 1996; Secomb, 2007). In other words, the literature overwhelmingly suggests that students generally perceive the peer review process as positive; it improves the quality of the essay, and their learning is increased (Dunn, 1996; White and Kirby, 2005). This outcome, of course, is subject to the quality of peer feedback.

Method

This study used a qualitative methodology and Denzin and Lincoln's (1994) constructivist-interpretive approach to provide insight into "...the complex world of lived experience from the point of view of those who live it" (Schwandt, 1994, p. 118). I also drew upon Bandura's (1986) social cognitive theory. When I originally began this project, the research attempted to ascertain the impact of teacher and peer feedback on student writing. During the research process, several issues arose that caused me to re-examine my data. What analysis pointed to was far more complex; to wit, an examination of not just the impact of feedback on writing but the impact of writing on self-efficacy. The roadmap created by later analysis led me to consider the relationship between requisite knowledge, feedback, revisions, and how these impact self-efficacy.

Research Site and Participants

All research, multiple observations and interviews, was conducted on the campus of a small, Catholic, liberal arts university in Western New York. Undergraduate enrollment includes approximately 3,300 students. Of the roughly 800 freshmen, approximately 120, or 15 percent, were identified as in need of remediation in composition. Placement of these students in developmental composition classes is based on a number of factors, including SAT scores, English Regents exam scores, and their final grades in English class.

Participants included one freshman developmental composition teacher and three of her students. The instructor, Ms. H., has been employed by this university on a part-time basis since 2010. She teaches two composition classes on campus; one regular and one developmental. She also teaches part-time at another local university. There, she teaches four sections of freshmen English Literature, which was her focus in college and reflects her Master's degree. The three students were chosen on the basis of their placement in developmental composition. It should be stated that while six freshmen are enrolled in this developmental level class, only three of the students came to class the day I observed. All three students who attended on this day brought the first drafts of their essays, as requested by their instructor, Ms. H. Two of the students, one a Caucasian male, and the other, an African American female, are athletes, participating in DI sports on campus, and both are receiving athletic scholarships. The third student, a Caucasian female, neither plays intercollegiate sports nor receives any tuition assistance.

The sampling method was intentional. I too am employed by this University. I too teach developmental composition. We two are the only developmental composition teachers employed here. Because of my long-standing affiliation with this University, gaining access to both the developmental instructor and her class was expedient and pertinent to my focus. I am committed to examining standard practices in developmental composition classes as they greatly impact student outcome. Data provided by the Department of Education's National Education Longitudinal Study reports that developmental students in four-year institutions suffer from substantially lower graduation rates than their non-developmental peers; 52 percent versus 78 percent (Brock, 2010,p.115). It was and is my hope that findings from this limited research

might prove insightful for other educators, and might yield better, more effective strategies I can implement in my own classroom.

Data Collection

For this study, data was gathered from multiple sources. All observations and interviews took place on the University campus. Ms. H., the instructor, was interviewed twice; once before first drafts were handed in, and again, after final grades for revisions were completed. Each semi-structured interview took approximately one hour to complete. She allowed both conversations to be audio-taped. I acted as an active participant while observing three of Ms. H.'s students conduct a peer response workshop, a session which took 60 minutes to complete. Ms. H. was not present in class that day. I then observed as Ms. H. held 15 minute individual conferences with each of these three students. All participants allowed audio-taping of their conversations. In individual, semi-structured interviews, I chatted with two of the three students twice; once after they had completed their first drafts and the peer response workshop, and again, after Ms. H. returned their final, graded essays to them. Each interview took approximately 45 minutes. Although the third student agreed to meet and discuss her writing, she failed to keep appointments on two separate occasions, and I decided to limit interviews to the two students who were more amenable to participating. To maintain trust and confidentiality, I interviewed each of these students without the other one present. For the purposes of this study, these students will be referred to as Nicki and Zeke; not their real names. Each audio taped session was transcribed and then coded to allow for later analysis of data to be done. In order to code, I first focused on all sentences that reflected words related to writing such as revision, essay, proofreading, drafting, thinking... Then I coded for sentences relating to communication and input, words such as feedback, offered, helped, suggested... I also separated all sentences that contained words relating to feelings such as happy, frustrated, confused, confident... Although many sentences contained both academic and visceral words, this was not always the case. There were three majors considerations; task understanding, their ability to utilize feedback purposefully for essay revisions, and how this knowledge and ability impacted their writing and self-efficacy.

Data Analysis

Audio tapes were transcribed immediately after each observation or interview. Non-verbal gestures noted during these sessions were added. I first attempted to code for student understanding of feedback received and offered using the following categories: (a) Nature of feedback (positive or negative), (b) Scope (general or specific), (c) Focus (higher or lower order concerns), (d) Category addressed (focus, development, organization, purpose/audience), and (e) Non-verbal cues. It quickly became apparent that this type of coding was insufficient for significant synthesis and understanding of what I sensed was really consequential. At that point, I took a step back and allowed each narrative to speak to me. I first listened to the tapes, then repeatedly read the transcripts. At the end of this process, I was able to code according to the themes that emerged. The first category reflected task understanding and strategy acquisition. To that end, I located and studied sentences using words related to composition such as drafting, organizing,

revising... The second set of codes reflected feedback. All sentences containing words such as offered, asked, peers, response... were included in this group. The third was coded for visceral reactions and focused on feelings, hopes, insecurities, and beliefs. This group includes such words as hope, like, fear, hate... I identified three major themes that characterize student writing engagement. The first theme to emerge was the relationship between knowledge acquisition and feedback and drafting ability. The second theme which emerged was the impact of feedback on student revisions. The third and potentially most interesting theme which emerged was how this writing experience impacted student self-efficacy in regards to future writing assignments.

Limitations

Because half of the students failed to complete assignments and attend class, the number of respondents is very small. Findings, however, should not necessarily be discounted solely on this basis. I focus on instructor methods and teacher-student interaction in order to identify best, most effective practices. Note *The Effect of E-Journaling on Student Engagement*, published in the *Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Science*, 5(7), 13-27 (Halm, 2017). Findings support the importance of purpose and context for students; "When I care about what I'm learning, I pay attention and I get it. I take the time to understand it" (Halm, 2017, p.28). Student response also points to the need for instructor feedback; "I knew what I wanted to say, but I didn't know exactly how to say it,

and Professor P. would write things and try to help...I think that helps" (Halm, 2017, p. 28). Therefore, I believe the anecdotal findings from the current study build on and strengthens findings from previous studies

Findings

In this section, we will first discuss the relationship between task understanding and strategy acquisition on student drafting and feedback. Next, we will discuss how teacher and peer feedback impacted revisions, both real and perceived. Finally, we will consider how this writing experience impacted student confidence and self-efficacy in composing future writing assignments.

Impact of Task Understanding and Strategy Acquisition on Student Drafting and Feedback

In my first conversation with each student, we discussed their recently completed first drafts. It was clear from our discussion that neither Zeke nor Nicki understood task expectations. In answer to, "What kind of writing project have you been working on?" there was silence. I attempted to rephrase for understanding, "Is it a position piece or a problem-solution essay, perhaps a causal analysis?" Neither student could actually label the assignment specifically. I considered the relationship between task understanding and component pieces. Experts embrace modeling as a key element of social cognitive theory, which "examines the processes involved as people learn observing others and gradually acquire control over their own behavior" (p.234). This could explain students' inability to revise when they're unsure about the considerations and components of the writing task. Zeke told me,

"Um, I mean, I just never really understood it to begin with so I kinda just wrote it". In a follow-up conversation with the instructor, I asked about assignment genre and her modeling activities. After a long, thoughtful pause, she said she would call it a position essay. Ms. H. reiterated that she provided many modeling activities, drawing examples from published essays. I asked if she could offer an example of modeling and she immediately offered tense consistency. She added that she also modeled for characteristics such as first person narrative. She'd read such a passage and then ask for feedback about the impact of using the style. Wanting to fully understand the depth and breadth of modeling, I asked specifically about issues like thesis statements, organization and development strategies. These things, she believed, needed no teacher modeling. Instead, the texts acted as models for student writing. "Any issues needing to be addressed", she added, "...could be handled in individual conferences".

It was clear that these two students did not grasp their purpose in writing, nor did they understand what revising called for. The instructor's modeling included exhibiting characteristics of good writing, as well as potential pitfalls. I understood her rationale because I internally interpreted and recoded her word choices, her language. This, potentially, is something students lacking in requisite knowledge are unable to do. For example, in our first interview, Ms. H. told me that one example of a class lesson included cautioning students against using "cliché statements", and she would explain to the class "why they aren't particularly effective". She did not, in our conversation, identify clichés as one form of fallacy. Because of her explanation, I have no reason to believe students were provided with either a definition of fallacy or examples of other forms of fallacy. In a follow-up conversation, the teacher informed me that in an attempt to build on students' prior knowledge, there was discussion on when they might have heard/read such fallacies, allowing them to understand the inherent flaws. According to the instructor, she modeled just one type of fallacy, potentially lacking context and without full explanation. She also pointed to "lack of connecting". She lamented that, "Students rarely have a solid understanding of what they're saying at this point and therefore cannot demonstrate the logic and relationships between ideas". Lack of connecting could mean two things. The first issue is development, writing which includes history and details that allow readers to understand the importance of the topic. She could also mean organization. How are paragraphs/section related – logically, temporally, chronologically? Zeke, in particular, mimicked the teacher's words; "connections" and "lack of connections" several times during both interviews, though when asked to define, he was unable to do so. He seemed unsure about the meaning. These issues explain, at least in part, Zeke and Nicki's uncertainty.

This instructor is obviously dedicated, and strives to help. While she seemed to embrace a team approach and the need for independence, during our conversation she also stressed the importance of guiding writers. If necessary, she'll "... guide them the whole way through". These two goals might seem at odds. She adds, "While this is a technique I find effective, I also see it as a specific task of the course; if they cannot figure these things

out for themselves by the time they leave my class, I have not helped them acquire the tools they need for success". Ms. H. told me she begins a unit by reading an essay, and follows up with a discussion about aspects of the writing which are fruitful, as well as those aspects that should act as examples of counter-productive methods. Students are to choose a topic and write an essay similar to the one they've read. She may be reading a position essay, as was the case with this assignment. However, according to the teacher, she failed to identify this as a position essay. She was hoping "... to achieve these goals in a way that makes them [students] realize the above through their own thought process". Her philosophy led her to rely upon students' ability to connect the dots for themselves. While this may work in her regular sections of writing, the method appears far less productive for developmental learners. During private interviews with each of the two students, interviews conducted immediately after first drafts had been responded to by instructor and peers, both seemed unclear about what had been learned or what the task requirements included. There is little evidence of theory in Ms. H.'s class.

The Impact of Teacher and Peer Feedback on Revisions

Zeke offered examples of instructor feedback, and attempted to explain his plans for revisions. The teacher, he said, told him he needed to fix, "The tie-ins, the connections, making connections". Unable to expand or offer clarification, it was not until I asked, "Do you mean development of your topic and the way you organize your information?" that he said, "Yeah". He was much quicker to offer input about assistance from peers. According to Zeke, he got nothing from his partners. Nicki too had problems defining issues that had been pointed to. From peers, she learned, "This intro is lengthy, blah, blah, blah", and I was like "Oh my God, it is. Like I do need to fix it". Unsure about revisions on her introduction, Nicki thought perhaps there were problems with her thesis statement. Though the peer review process was unproductive for these students, research points to the many benefits; "...students craft more diverse, complex final products—which deserve a wider audience than the teacher. As learners critique one another's work, they might notice praiseworthy points or pose questions that the instructor has not thought of. A student might ignore feedback from a teacher but suddenly pay attention to the class". Good response, however, calls for students' "...dynamic participation. Listeners must not only attend to each presentation, but also offer concrete suggestions for its improvement while commending aspects of the work that they appreciate" (Reynolds, 2009). I cannot definitively point to the reasons the process failed; inadequate written prompts or inadequate composition knowledge. What deserves focus is the juxtaposition of the two students. While Zeke believed the instructor to be more helpful than his peers, Nicki found the little feedback offered by peers more beneficial than her conference with the instructor.

There was a discrepancy between what the instructor said she did and what I witnessed during my conference observations. Though Ms. H. said, "I circle, highlight, underline, restructure, draw arrows, etc in text so that the students see specific instances of weaknesses/strengths throughout their writing", she never looked at drafts before conferences, which were held in the center

of the Student Center. During our interview, she added, "I generally go through one paragraph extensively with them, then have them do the same to the following paragraph with me so that I can help guide them, but they demonstrate understanding and capability". This did not happen. While both students brought first drafts, as the teacher instructed, she did not look at them. Instead, she referred to the written comments on first assignment essays, and read them aloud, pointing to problematic issues that existed on these revised essays.

In total, the instructor spent approximately eight of the fifteen minutes discussing Nicki's first draft with her, and only two minutes discussing Zeke's first draft. Although Zeke told me he believed Ms. H. wanted him to work on "making connections", the instructor never pointed to additional organization or development necessary on Zeke's essay accept in regards to the previous assignment. In response to a question about the difficulty of his first draft, Zeke laughingly told his teacher he had "... literally woke up at 7 A.M and did it and surprisingly, they [peers] said it was really good, so surprisingly there was a 7A.M paper and I wrote 5 pages before I went to class". The teacher moved on to the next question without comment. No specific observations or comments were made for revision strategies on either of the students' essays. Although this didn't bother Zeke, the same cannot be said of Nicki. She was underwhelmed by feedback from her instructor. "I would, I don't know, I would feel better if like she liked looked it over, I just really do. Personally, I think the teacher knows best. Like your peers know but the final result is you're a teacher so I really do think she should read it". About what she might revise, she added, "Probably my thesis because the thesis is really the main start to the paper. I feel like I'm gonna make the same mistake. That's why I kind of wish that Ms. H. did read it so she could help me". To the contrary, Zeke seemed to think revisions would take minimal energy, only requiring more "add-ons and connecting". The amount of effort called for may have been underestimated because of the positive feedback on a draft written in two hours, directly before class the day it was due. The teacher did not take exception to his method which could be interpreted as tacit approval. The next topic discussed in interviews with each student focused on final grades as they compared to expectations and students' perceptions about the quality of their revisions.

Both students received "B-/B". Neither student knew which grade would be recorded for this assignment. Nicki shared, "I would want a single grade. Like, where am I? Is it in the middle or what?". Zeke said, "So I don't know exactly what that means, if it's in the middle somewhere...". Perhaps more telling, neither student was able to reflect on what changes were actually made during the revision process. Nicki thought it was research. She used three sources, although the teacher did not mandate research. When pressed, she told me the research had been included in the first draft, and no expansion was included in her revisions. The only change in text related to her misinterpretation of the Iraq war. Her facts were wrong; a point her father called to her attention. Zeke, as in previous conversations, said revisions focused on,

“Umm, just making better connections like she said on my first one”. Zeke explained the revision process as, “Just, whatever your topic is, write more off of that instead of writing more about the topic”. Neither student sought assistance from tutors at the Writing Center, but both Nicki and Zeke did solicit help from family members at home. Asking for feedback from a teacher, friend, or even family member may help in substantive revisions, but in this case, that was not true. Both Zeke and Nicki concurred about what feedback they asked for and received; proofreading resulting in sentence-level corrections.

The Impact of Writing on Learning, Confidence and self-Efficacy in Future Writing Tasks

In an effort to better understand how progress impacted their sense of self-efficacy, I asked each of the students, in individual interviews, what strategies and insights had been accrued through the writing process. Nicki was quicker than Zeke to respond. “...I always use three different tenses, and I remember trying to keep it, well, I forget which one, but I tried to keep it the same”. She was not sure about tense appropriateness, just that tense should remain consistent. She deduced that she must be improving because she received C on her first assignment and at least a B- on the second. Nicki did not seem to associate learning with improvement. Instead, it was the grade that answered this question. Although she received higher marks on this assignment, Nicki innately understood the need for more knowledge. She told me her organization needed to be worked on, though she wasn't sure why or how. Zeke too looked at grades as the measure of learning. He believed he had made great strides on his writing because his first essay assignment “...only earned C-/D and this one was marked B-/B”. Despite the higher mark he received, Zeke could not identify why he revised as he did. “I just assumed that it needed to be expanded”. “I just added another paragraph, but that was it; just a little bit more length and that was it”. He added no additional research, nor was there reorganization. Little thought, he said, went into expanding. “I added more text” (he needed to meet the 4 page requirement). The revised essay was returned with feedback from the teacher. Unable to specify what he'd learned, Zeke was happy because “There's a lot less writing, like on the margins and then on the back of it too, like lots less”. “And what did it say?” I asked. “It was just basically like repetitiveness. I can't even remember about it. I just looked at it real quick”. Going forward, unlike Nicki, Zeke feels both motivated and empowered.

“I'm already like, basically done with it so I just have to hand in the draft or whatever 'cause this weekend I had a religion one to do so I just knocked them out both”. The instructor recently sent students to the library for help gathering scholarly research, and annotations are due before first drafts are to be composed. Lacking research, Zeke felt confident in writing because “The second paper, yeah, you needed to focus on something, but I just feel like the third paper, I just feel like it's ours so we get to pick what our topic and our argument is. So I just feel like that's even easier. Just because you get to write about whatever”. While unsure about exact requirements, he had yet to use six sources which he believed to be the minimum required. He explained the topic as “Just how popular sports aren't

popular in the rest of the world so we try to branch off and push them on other cultures”.

Nicki felt far less prepared for the assignment. Her motivation to complete the upcoming assignment centered on her love of dance and her experience as a ballet dancer. While she wanted to write about ballet dancers, she was unsure about what to write and had found few acceptable articles. Nicki was counting on guidance and information from the instructor to fill the many gaps she believed to exist, but she was dubious about the amount of help she would receive.

While both students would love to receive A on their final assignment, neither could describe what excellence means, what attributes an A paper embodies. The same was true for their last assignment. I asked each student why, did they think, they had not earned a higher grade – what was missing from their essays. Although he said he had no plans of actually asking the instructor, Zeke answered, “I honestly have no idea”. Nicki's response was much the same, “I honestly don't know”. This doesn't bode well for their levels of learning, writing, or self-efficacy.

Discussion and Conclusions

Impact of Task Understanding and Strategy Acquisition on Drafting and Feedback

According to a social cognitive model of sequential skill acquisition (Schunk & Zimmerman, 1997; Zimmerman, 2000, 2002),

The first of four sequential levels, observation, is necessary for acquisition of new writing skills. Modeled reading and writing in which the teacher models, verbally, to the students, a writing process or strategy, might allow students to identify the components of effective writing, components they can begin to consider as they draft essays, as well as during the peer feedback process. Modeling is defined as “...changes in people that result from observing the actions of others” (Eggen and Kauchak, 2001, p.236).

These experts embrace modeling as a key element of social cognitive theory, which “examines the processes involved as people learn observing others and gradually acquire control over their own behavior” (p.234). Social cognitive theory was ignored by the instructor despite the potential benefits of modeling and scaffolding activities for knowledge acquisition of writing (Bandura, 1986; Zimmerman, 2000). Social learning theory (Bandura, 1977; Vygotsky, 1978) suggests that students learn best when learning is situated in a context in which they engage in a meaningful way with each other and the teacher. Genre writing is socially constructed. Helping students to identify and create different genres reinforces reflection of writer purpose and audience needs (Martin & Rothery, 1986). Teaching writing through a focus on genre supports familiarity with the both conventions and expectations of a genre. In a social approach to learning, the teacher aids students in composing texts, and methods such as scaffolding can eventually culminate in the ability to compose independently. After exposing students to examples of a genre, an

instructor can model writing that engages students in shared writing (Gibbons, 2002). Ms. H.'s practices failed to reflect pedagogical theory which espouses writing as a process, focusing on student interest, voice, and personal technique (Emig, 1971; Elbow, 1973; Murray, 2011). Lacking the requisite knowledge and foundation necessary for essay composition, these students were unsure what the task required. This left both students reliant on peer and teacher feedback. Unfortunately, those same shortcomings in preparation negatively impacted their ability to offer substantive response to one another or seek feedback that might allow for meaningful revision.

The Impact of Teacher and Peer Feedback on Revisions

Despite literature that shows the productivity of peer feedback, (Dunn, 1996; White and Kirby, 2005), neither student was able to identify what input they actually received or how this could improve their writing. Studies show teacher feedback is of paramount importance in teaching students to write (Peterson & Kennedy, 2004; Sommers, 2006; Stagg, Peterson & Kennedy, 2006; Stern & Solomon, 2006). Treglia (2009), author of *Teacher-Written Commentary in College Writing Composition: How Does It Impact Student Revisions?* believes "Teacher-student interaction is crucial in getting students involved in the process of revision as Mina Shaughnessy reminds us: writing is an act of confidence". Further hindering their progress was the absence of specific feedback from the instructor who responded not to drafts but revised essays. An abundance of research supports direct and specific feedback in response to student writing. The absence of this feedback leaves students unable to identify shortcomings and productively hone essays (Peterson & Kennedy, 2004; Sommers, 2006; Stagg, Peterson & Kennedy, 2006; Stern & Solomon, 2006). While one student was overtly insecure about revisions and unsure how to proceed, the other seemed to have a simplistic view of both the composition and revision process, unaware of any demands other than expansion. While neither student sought assistance from the Writing Center, both called upon family members for feedback. What both received was input on comma splices and other sentence-level issues. Final essays were marked with two grades, leaving their understanding of potential progress unclear. Comments written on final essays were global in nature and cited only progress of those shortcomings present in previous essays as they pertain to the most recent assignment. In contrast, Vardi's 2009 study pointed to the most productive feedback being specific in nature. Neither student was able to identify attributes of exemplary essays, nor were they able to label the genre of essay they had just completed.

The Impact of Learning on Confidence and self-Efficacy

According to Zimmerman and Bonner's Social Cognitive Model of Sequential Skill Acquisition,

Self-efficacy is defined as the perceived capability to perform at designated levels (Bandura, 1986). Writing outcomes provide process-proficient writers with the ultimate criterion by which their skill can be measured. With increasing levels of self-regulation, writers are expected to experience greater self-motivation, such as more positive self-efficacy beliefs and self-reactions,

and greater intrinsic interest in the particular form of writing (Zimmerman, p.242).

In other words, writing allows students an opportunity to acquire skills. Grades reflect mastery, and good grades act to positively impact self-efficacy which in turn increases motivation and interest in writing. Conversely, little skill, coupled with grades commensurate with minimal mastery might negatively impact self-efficacy. On the upcoming assignment, one student felt insecure and ill-prepared while the other felt a strong sense of self-efficacy, so motivated that he had completed the first draft before the research process had been completed. Nicki and Zeke, it seems, have become fluent with the steps of the writing process, but neither utilized these steps in ways that might deepen their subject or writing knowledge. Over the course of this assignment, neither Nicki nor Zeke learned how to identify elements essential to the chosen genre of writing or gained understanding about the foci or strategies of effective peer feedback practices. Perhaps due to a lack of feedback, neither student made meaningful changes during the revision process. While a grade of B-/B signaled success to Zeke, to Nicki, it signaled failure. Zeke, feeling empowered, was motivated to move on to the next project immediately, while Nicki's sense of self-efficacy was diminished, leaving her insecure and far less motivated to begin again.

Implications

Student self-efficacy stems from task success. In order to be successful in writing, students must, first and foremost, understand genre requirements. In order to accomplish this, instructors should model, for the students, examples of genre writing, especially examples produced by students. This activity helps students to envision outcomes, and allows knowledge to become internalized (Zimmerman, 2000). Subsequent scaffolding, including cooperative and active learning, fosters academic growth and incremental independence (Clay & Cazden, 1990; Dewey, 1902; Vygotsky, 1978). Teaching the writing process allows students to find their voices, develop writing techniques, and pursue topics of interest. This process emphasizes "...discovery through language" (Murray, 2011). Productive feedback is only possible when students are vested and informed. Modeling examples of substantive feedback can aid in this goal. As a composition teacher, I find that students respond to peers' writing in much the same way as I respond to them. Utilizing Vygotsky's "MKOs" (more knowledgeable others) serves two purposes; collaboration and reciprocal learning (Vygotsky, 1978). Conversely, students must receive feedback from the instructor which is timely, understandable, and specific in nature (Sommers, 2006; Stagg, Peterson & Kennedy, 2006). Revised essays should be returned with feedback about progress, as well as areas in which further revisions might have been fruitful, thus initiating reflection and deeper understanding. Lacking in such knowledge, Nicki felt ill-equipped and insecure in her own abilities.

Further studies of developmental classroom practices should be conducted. Due to the complex nature of student writing, teachers should be cognizant of pertinent theories and effective methods. Freshman courses, including developmental composi-

tion, are often taught by adjunct faculty. The American Association of Community Colleges reported that in public two-year colleges, as many as 67 percent have adjunct status. More telling perhaps, only 20 percent of those institutions require any kind of specific training for those full-time faculty teaching developmental students, and only 17 percent of colleges require such training for their part-time faculty (p.4). While approximately 20 percent of faculty at two-year colleges teach developmental classes, only 12 percent were hired specifically for this task (Outcalt, 2003, p.8). As was the case with Ms. H., some instructors, though well-meaning, lack the pedagogical knowledge required for optimal practices. Further, larger studies should be conducted. Because of constraints, only two students participated, allowing only limited insights into student perspectives and perceptions. Additional research focusing on the impact of teacher preparation in developmental writing philosophies and practices would also prove, potentially, enlightening.

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Social Media Connectedness of Mass Communication Students

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Abstract

This study explores findings from a study that examines the relationship between habits, social connectedness, and perceived usefulness of social media by mass communication students, when controlling for age, gender, college classification, ethnicity, major, primary social media platform, social media use, and time spent on social media each week. The results will focus on study participants’ college majors and their degree of agreement with statements in the survey.

Keywords: Social media, connectedness, students, mass communication, public relations

1 Introduction

The conventional discussion in today’s communication circles is that Millennials possess a unique competency in electronic communication and because of this, they can realize an array of accomplishments utilizing such technologies (Gorman, et. al, 2004). In *Generations: The History of America’s Future, 1584 to 2069 (1991)*, William Strauss and Neil Howard ponder the habits and forces shaping the approximately 76 million Millennials born between 1982 and 2000. The authors posit that these Millennials will hopefully “act on vital issues their parents can only ponder” (Strauss and Howe, 1991, p. 342). But the underlying question remains, “Can and will this generation actually use technology to broaden their understanding and connectedness to the broader world?” The authors state in *The Next 20 Years: How Customers and Workforce Attitudes Will Evolve (2007)* that “Millennials will use their digital empowerment to build and maintain close peer bonds.” What are the implications of this connectedness?

Since the birth of Millennials, the world has seen the introduction of the first iPhone (2007), introduction of Gigabit Ethernet by such companies as AT&T and Google (now Alphabet), and public offerings of new social media networks including Snapchat and Instagram. Generation Y or Millennials are widely considered those born between the years 1982 - 2000. Generation Z, or those born since 2000 have never known a time without wireless Internet. It is widely believed that because of this ubiquitous use of social media, that they feel more connected and use social media frequently.

According to Pew (2016), 79% of all adults use Facebook. Further, by Facebook’s own measure, there are over 1.1 billion active daily users on mobile device (Facebook, 2017). The statistics for total number of active

users dwarfs even that figure at 1.28 billion users in March 2017 (Facebook, 2017). According to Pew Research (2016), 88 percent of 18-29 use Facebook, while those with some college (82%) and college degrees (79%) use Facebook.

On Instagram, a Facebook owned property, use for 18-29 was 59%, while those with some college was 37% and 33% for those with a college degree. It can be safely said that social media use is increasing in the United States. While it is true that most Americans and young college students are using Facebook (a form of social media), how does this near ubiquity of use between this target audience engage a true feeling of connectedness.

Edward Bernays, often credited as the father of public relations considered public relations as covering “three fields including information, persuasion, and integration” (Bernays, 1975, p. 2). In this sense, today’s students involved in the field of public relation are immensely familiar with using social media in context of information gathering and sharing.

2 Background

Shared experiences and the ability to feel in-touch, and perhaps eager to understand the larger world, can be described as connectedness. Therefore, social media is a conduit for feels of connectedness. As the social media universe expands, how do college students react to this growth? Sinclair & Grieve (2017) examined social connectedness in older adults and Facebook, found that social media “emerged as a separate factor to offline social connectedness,” however, the average age in this study was 61. Ahn & Dong (2013) examined whether social media use for seeking connectedness or for avoiding social isolation. In this S. Korean study, over 300 Korean adults were surveyed on their use of social media, face-to-face communication, social isolation and connectedness and their well-being. This study suggests that social media can be augment face-to-face

communication, but by itself, was limited to seeking connectedness to others. Venezuela, Park and Lee (2009) found that there was a positive relationship between college students' "use of Facebook and intensity of Facebook groups use" (p. 893) and students' civic and political participation. However, does use of social media.

Connectedness is also described to mean how the boundaries expand or "transcend the categories between 'us' and 'them' to achieve harmony." (Liu & Robertson, 2011, p. 37). In essence, this feeling of connectedness is what helps not only millennials, but society recognize our commonness and shared bonds.

Social Media and Connectedness

Knight, Rochon, and Hailey (2015) found that in helping students transition to a higher education environment, social media helped students become more proactive about contacting those members of the teaching staff that were present in the social media environment. Mostafa (2015) discovered that students who perceive themselves to be academically engaged on social media helps them to achieve their career goals. Skoric, Zhu, Goh, and Pang (2016) conducted a meta-analysis review of social media and citizen engagement and found that social media generally has a positive relationship with civic engagement and political participation.

3 Research Objective

The first phase of this study sought to answer if there is a difference in how students with different college majors and their view on social media and feelings of connectedness.

4 Methods

This research examined participants' involvement with various social media platforms in social life, education, and communication with their peers and professors, and how that involvement influences their perception of a sense of communal belongingness or connectedness, personal growth. The Institutional Review Board Sam Houston State University, approved the study.

Instrument

The research questions were "What are the perceived usefulness of social media by public relations students?" This question was broken-down into seven specific statements and participants were asked to indicate their degree of agreement with each statement on Likert-type scale, ranging from *strong agree* to *strongly disagree*. The following questions were used:

1. Social media use has given me a deeper understand of important issues affecting me and my community.
2. Social media inspires me to see the world through the eyes of others
3. Social media helps me understand my connection to the community
4. Students who use social media are more concerned
5. Social media has an equalizing effect, allowing for a multitude of voices and opinions, and viewpoints to be heard
6. Social media will be helpful for me, professionally, in the future
7. Social media has and will continue to be a strong force for communication in my prospective career field
8. Two additional questions were asked as it relates to students perceived usefulness of social media in the context of their college environment. The following questions were used:

9. Social media helps me stay connected with my classmates
10. Social media helps me stay connected with my instructors

Participants were asked several demographic questions including age, race, gender, college classification, and major. Additionally, participants were asked about their primary social network, use of time spent on social networks each week, and their change in social media use from a year ago.

Procedures

Students were asked to participate in the survey through postings on this Blackboard accounts and via their university email. A solicitation script was sent to students via their email addresses and/or posted in Blackboard as an announcement. The purpose of the study, its benefits and risks, and its terms were entered in Qualtrics™, effectively allowing prospective participants full (and, if needed, repeated) access to all information concerning the study, along with an opportunity to agree to and enter and complete the study, or to anonymously withdraw from the study at any time. Participants consented to the research terms by voluntarily entering the survey, advancing through the self-paced and self-directed informed consent process, and entering an "agree to participate" statement at the end of the consent process. Responses were collected via an online survey designed and entered in Qualtrics™.

The nature of the study was exploratory; however, a mix of descriptive and inferential statistics are presented to analyze the data.

5 Results

Demographics

Descriptive statistics were computed for all variables. Categorical variables include student's gender, college classification, race, major, primary social media platform, and social media use. Continuous variables include participant's age. When helpful for clarity, data for continuous variables are presented in figures that represent frequencies while data for categorical variables are represented by tables. Graphs are provided for all variables.

The sample for this survey consisted of mostly mass communication students at Sam Houston State University. Of the 159 of surveys distributed, 22 were not usable. The final usable participant surveys were $N = 137$. The following section will provide the results for the descriptive statistics and the findings from the current study.

All tables and figures are in the section titled *Tables and Figures*.

Age

Table 1 provides the frequency of participants by age. Of the 137 participants, there were 65 who fell between 18 – 20 years of age ($N=65$, 47.45%), 61 who fell between 21-23 years of age ($N=61$, 44.53%), 9 who fell between 24-25 years of age ($N=9$, 6.57%), and 2 who were 26 or older ($N=2$, 1.46%).

Gender

Table 2 provides the frequency of participants by gender. Of the 137 participants, there were 47 females for 31.31% ($N=47$) and 90 males for 65.69% ($N=90$).

College Classification

Figure 1 is a bar graph distribution of number of students in the sample and their time college classification. For college classification, 25 or 18% were freshmen, 37 or 27% were sophomores, 39 or 28% were classified as juniors, 35 or 26% were seniors, and 0 or 0% were graduate students; one student was unsure of his or her college classification and represented 1% of those sampled.

Race and Ethnicity

Figure 2 is a bar graph distribution of number of students in the sample and their time race and ethnicity. Fifty-five or 40.15% of respondents were White, 33 or 24.09% were Hispanic/Latino, and 32 or 23.36% were Black/African American. Eleven or 8.03% of respondents were multiracial. Two respondents or 1.46% were Asian/Pacific Islander, and one respondent or .73% was Middle Eastern. Another two or 1.46% of respondents selected *Other*.

Major

Figure 3 is a bar graph distribution of number of students in the sample and their college major. Of those surveyed, four or 2.92% were journalism majors, eight or 5.84% were film majors, 52 or 37.96% majored in PR/Advertising, 21 or 15.33% majored in multi-platform journalism, nine or 6.57% majored in broadcast production, and 43 or 31.39% were classified as "other" (this could include students taking mass communication classes, but undecided or undeclared at the time of the survey); written responses for *Other* included history, two-dimensional studio art, agriculture, English, and communication studies.

Primary Social Media Platform

Figure 4 is a bar graph distribution of number of students in the sample and their primary social media platform. Facebook was the primary social media platform with 38 or 27.74%. Twitter followed closely with 36 users or 26.28%, Instagram with 28 users or (20.44%), and Snapchat with 27 users or 19.71%. The remaining platforms consisted of Tumblr with three users or 2.19% and GroupMe at 1.46%. Three users or 2.19% indicated they did not use social media.

Social Media Use

Figure 5 is a bar graph distribution of number of students in the sample and their social media use. Amongst those surveyed, 58 or 42.34% indicated their social media use has increased. Fifty-two respondents (37.96%) said that their social media use has stayed about the same. Twenty or 14.60% users indicated their social media use has decreased and seven users or 5.11% indicated they were not sure whether their social media use has increased or decreased.

Time Spent on Social Media Each Week

Figure 6 is a bar graph distribution of number of students in the sample and their time spent on social media each week. Sixty-two or 45% of respondents indicated they spend 3 – 5 hours each week on social media; twenty-four or 17.52% indicated they spend 1 – 2 hours per week on social media; 20 respondents indicated they spend 6 – 10 hours per week on social media; 19 respondents indicated they spend more than 10 hours per week on social media. Ten or 7.30% of respondents indicated they spend less than one hour per week on social media and two or 1.46% of respondents indicated they do not use social media at all.

Statement 1: Social media use has given me a deeper understand of important issues affecting me and my community.

Approximately 70% of sample responded in agreement (*agree to strongly agree*) with Statement 1. Table 3 is a means table representing the distribution of means scores by major from Statement 1. When combined with major, public relations/advertising and multiplatform journalism majors tended to report stronger agreement ($M=6.10$) with Statement 1, than students who classified as Other majors ($M=5.26$). Notably, Film students rated the lowest agreement with this statement ($M= 5.13$).

Statement 2: Social media inspires me to see the world through the eyes of others

More than 46% of sample responded in agreement (*agree to strongly agree*) with Statement 2. Table 4 is a means table representing the distribution of means scores by major from Statement 2. When combined with major, public relations/advertising and multiplatform journalism majors reported lower agreement ($M=5.71$) with Statement 1, than broadcast production majors ($M=5.89$), but more than students who classified their major as Other ($M=5.26$). Notably, film students rated the lowest agreement with this statement ($M= 5.13$).

Statement 3: Social media helps me understand my connection to the community

Approximately 26% of sample responded in agreement (*agree to strongly agree*) with Statement 3. Table 5 represents the mean scores by major from Statement 3. When combined with major, journalism students rated highest agreement ($M=6.00$). Public relations/advertising majors reported the next highest agreement ($M=5.65$) with Statement 1, multiplatform journalism ($M=5.62$), broadcast production majors ($M=5.56$), and film students ($M=5.00$). Students who classified themselves as other majors ranked lowest in agreement with Statement 3 ($M=4.74$). Notably, film students rated the lowest agreement with this statement ($M=5.13$).

Statement 4: Students who use social media are more concerned

Approximately 16% of sample responded in agreement (*agree to strongly agree*) with Statement 4; over 31% *neither agreed nor disagreed* with this statement. Table 6 represents the mean scores by major from Statement 4. When combined with major, multiplatform journalism ranked the highest agreement ($M=4.90$) while public relations/advertising students responded in agreement with a median score of $M=4.35$. Film students ranked the lowest agreement of all students ($M=3.88$), and students who classified themselves as other, ranked the next lowest agreement ($M=4.16$) with Statement 4.

Statement 5: Social media has an equalizing effect, allowing for a multitude of voices and opinions, and viewpoints to be heard

More than 66% of sample responded in agreement (*agree to strongly agree*) with Statement 5. Table 7 represents the mean scores by major from Statement 5. When combined with major, public relations/advertising majors reported highest agreement ($M=6.19$) with Statement 5. Students with the next-highest agreement with Statement 5 include multiplatform journalism ($M=5.76$) and students who classified their major as Other ($M=5.58$).

Statement 6: Social media will be helpful for me, professionally, in the future

Over 57% of sample responded in agreement (*agree to strongly agree*) with Statement 6. Table 8 represents the mean scores by major from Statement 6. When combined with college major, journalism and public relations/advertising student ranked highest in agreement at $M=6.75$ and $M=6.06$ respectively.

Statement 7: Social media has and will continue to be a strong force for communication in my prospective career field

More than 70% of sample responded in agreement (*agree to strongly agree*) with Statement 7. Table 9 represents the mean scores (by major) from Statement 7. When combined with college major, journalism and public relations/advertising student ranked highest in agreement at $M=6.50$ and $M=6.48$ respectively. Students in who classified as Other, ranked lowest in agreement ($M=4.91$) with this statement.

Statement 8: Social media helps me stay connected with my classmates

Over 69% of sample responded in agreement (*agree to strongly agree*) with Statement 8. Table 10 represents the mean scores by major from Statement 8. Journalism students ranked highest in agreement ($M=6.75$) and public relations/advertising students ranked second-highest in agreement ($M=5.65$).

Statement 9: Social media helps me stay connected with my instructors

Only 29% of sample responded in agreement (*agree to strongly agree*) with Statement 9. Table 11 represents the mean scores by major from Statement 9. Journalism students ranked highest in agreement ($M=5.75$), while public relations/advertising students ranked lowest in agreement ($M=3.94$) of all students sampled.

6 Discussion

The preliminary results from this study examining the social media use of mass communication students and their feelings of connectedness found that amongst these students, public relations students did not rank highest overall in their agreement with connectedness. When looking at mass communication students in aggregate, a few significant observations were made.

Journalism students ranked highest in agreement on five of the nine statements, including helping them understand their connection to the community, how social media could be helpful to them professionally in the future, their belief that social media will be a strong force for communication in their prospective career field, their agreement that social media helps them stay connected to classmates, and their agreement that social media helps them stay connected with their professors. Social networking site discussions involving politics have also been found to have a positive impact on civic engagement (Gil de Zúñiga, 2012). Perhaps journalism students, seeing various community conversations from a first-hand perspective, find a higher relationship to the communities they cover and spur them to more feelings of engagement and connectedness. Journalist also share curiosity to investigate and report on the world around them (Niblock, 2010) perhaps making them keenly connected. The implication being that social media is another tool to affect that connectedness.

While it was initially thought that public relations students would rank highest amongst all categories because of their interaction with subject matter and classes that stress teamwork, community engagement, and openness to new ideas, the study found that PR/advertising majors ranked highest in agreement on only one question being that social media use has given them a deeper understanding of important issues affecting them and their community. Cell phones, have been found to open doors to foster relationships and access to membership in a community (Wei, 2006). By extension, those apps running on these phone foster that membership connection, but perhaps not to the oversized degree we would expect with public relations students.

On question nine, the question that dealt with social media and feelings of connectedness to their instructors, public relations/advertising students rated lowest amongst all students. Social media has limits for academics related to delivery and cultural resistance (Manca, 2016), and Tweeting was not related to interpersonal relationships between students and their instructors (Evans, 2014).

7 Limitations

Of note in this study is the small sample size ($N=137$). Additionally, no instrument reliability tests were conducted which would need to be conducted to determine reliability of the instrument and before any true inferences, regarding the data collected, could be made.

No longitudinal data was collected and so the information gathered is a one-time snapshot without the benefit of a pre-test administered to see if there has been a shift in these perceptions about social media use over time.

8 References

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9 Tables and Figures

Table 3

Statement 1: Social media use has given me a deeper understand of important issues affecting me and my community analysis by major

Field	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
Journalism	6.00	0.71	0.50	4
Film	5.13	1.83	3.36	8
PR/Advertising	6.10	1.08	1.16	52
Multiplatform Journalism	6.10	0.97	0.94	21
Broadcast Production	6.11	0.74	0.54	9
Other	5.26	1.45	2.10	43

Table 4

Statement 2: Social media inspires me to see the world through the eyes of others analysis by major.

Field	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
Journalism	5.75	0.83	0.69	4
Film	5.13	1.05	1.11	8
PR/Advertising	5.71	1.12	1.24	52
Multiplatform Journalism	5.71	1.16	1.35	21
Broadcast Production	5.89	0.74	0.54	9
Other	4.74	1.50	2.24	43

Table 5

Statement 3: Social media helps me understand my connection to the community analysis by major

Field	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
Journalism	6.00	1.00	1.00	4
Film	5.00	0.87	0.75	8
PR/Advertising	5.65	1.22	1.50	52
Multiplatform Journalism	5.62	1.13	1.28	21
Broadcast Production	5.56	0.83	0.69	9
Other	4.74	1.45	2.10	43

Table 6

Statement 4: Students who use social media are more concerned analysis by major

Field	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
Journalism	4.75	1.92	3.69	4
Film	3.88	1.05	1.11	8
PR/Advertising	4.35	1.21	1.46	52
Multiplatform Journalism	4.90	1.31	1.71	21
Broadcast Production	4.44	1.26	1.58	9
Other	4.16	1.40	1.95	43

Table 7

Statement 5: To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statement: Social media has an equalizing effect, allowing for a multitude of voices, opinions, and viewpoints to be heard analysis by major

Field	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
Journalism	5.50	1.12	1.25	4
Film	5.25	1.56	2.44	8
PR/Advertising	6.19	0.79	0.62	52
Multiplatform Journalism	5.76	1.15	1.32	21
Broadcast Production	4.78	1.62	2.62	9
Other	5.58	1.50	2.24	43

Table 8

Social Media Connectedness of Mass Communication Students

Statement 6: Social media will be helpful for me, professionally, in the future analysis by major

Field	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
Journalism	6.75	0.43	0.19	4
Film	5.63	1.11	1.23	8
PR/Advertising	6.06	1.12	1.25	52
Multiplatform Journalism	5.52	1.22	1.49	21
Broadcast Production	5.11	1.20	1.43	9
Other	5.12	1.32	1.73	43

Table 9

Statement 7: Social Media has and will continue to be a strong force for communication in my prospective career field analysis by major

Field	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
Journalism	6.50	0.87	0.75	4
Film	6.00	1.12	1.25	8
PR/Advertising	6.48	0.77	0.60	52
Multiplatform Journalism	6.29	0.70	0.49	21
Broadcast Production	5.78	0.79	0.62	9
Other	4.91	1.41	1.99	43

Table 10

Statement 8: Social media helps me stay connected with my classmates analysis by major

Field	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
Journalism	6.75	0.43	0.19	4
Film	5.63	0.70	0.48	8
PR/Advertising	5.65	1.25	1.57	52
Multiplatform Journalism	6.10	0.97	0.94	21
Broadcast Production	6.22	0.63	0.40	9
Other	5.74	1.06	1.12	43

Table 11

Statement 9: Social media helps me stay connected with my instructors analysis by major

Field	Mean	Std Deviation	Variance	Count
Journalism	5.75	2.17	4.69	4
Film	4.38	1.58	2.48	8
PR/Advertising	3.94	1.59	2.52	52
Multiplatform Journalism	4.24	1.87	3.51	21
Broadcast Production	4.89	1.52	2.32	9
Other	4.49	1.90	3.60	43

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 5

Figure 3

Figure 6

Figure 4

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